

CARBON-FIBER COMPOSITE CABLES FOR DEEP-WATER ANCHORAGE

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ABSTRACT

Anchorage cables are essential for offshore structures used to extract oil in deep water. They must be rigid enough to prevent platform motion, which may severely damage it. These cables are usually made of steel alloys, but this material is heavy and susceptible to corrosion in aggressive environment. The aim of this paper is to investigate the substitution of steel cables by carbon-fibre composite cables (CFCC), since the latter shows good tensile stress, corrosion resistance, and higher fatigue life when compared to steel. Two particular cases were studied. In the first case, the cable was submitted to normal stress, and in the second case, the cable was submitted to four-point flexural loading for bending behaviour evaluation. The analysis focused on 1×19 CFCC, with one core surrounded by nine rods, and another external layer containing another nine rods. They were numerically modelled using the finite element method (FEM) implemented in the finite element platform Abaqus®. The longitudinal Young's modulus of a single rod was experimentally measured in tensile testing of specimens instrumented with strain-gages. The remaining engineering properties were obtained using an invariant-based theory. To compare with the predictions of the numerical model, external rods of the composite cable were instrumented with strain-gages and the cable was tested in tension. Four-point-bending tests were also carried out in strain-gage instrumented specimens for comparison. After verifying good correlation between the two previous numerical predictions relative to the experimental data, the architecture of 1×7 traditional cables with same-diameter rods was modelled and analysed using finite elements. Results were compared with the first model, keeping the same cross section area.

1 INTRODUCTION

According to Meyer [1], Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) cables were first applied in 1996 at the vehicular cable-stayed Stork Bridge. The main reason for using composite cables was the large span allowed by this material. He also highlighted corrosion resistance, high specific stiffness, strength, and an outstanding fatigue behaviour among the advantages of Carbon Fibre Composite Cables (CFCC). These qualities make such cables natural candidates to substitute the traditional steel cables in offshore applications, due to the aggressive environment in deep sea.

A common structure for offshore platforms is the Tension Leg Platform (TLP), which is vertically moored at each corner by tension legs. Unlike in fixed structures its cost does not dramatically increase with the water depth [2]. In the special case of the Tension Leg Wellhead Platform (TLWP) shown in Fig. 1, where the wellhead lies inside the platform deck instead of the seafloor, the cables must be rigid enough to prevent the platform motion provoked by wave and wind interaction, whose effects were evaluated by Adrezi and Benaroya [2] and Niedzwecki & Huston [3].

Figure 1: TLWP P-61 floating on Brazilian sea at 1,180 m depth [4].

Despite the high stiffness required from TLPs anchorage cables, they must also be helical constructed to improve its bending behaviour, so the cable could be bent over small diameter spools. The counterpoint in designing small pitch cables (low helix angle) is the decrease on the tensile behaviour, so both tensile and bending behaviour must be fully understood when developing anchorage cables.

The aim of this work is to create, through Finite Element Method (FEM), numerical models that could accurately predict CFCC response under two situations. In the first model, the cable was fixed at one end with a tensile stress applied at the other. These boundary conditions were used to mimic commercial CFCC specimens instrumented with strain gauges and tested in tensile loading for comparison. On the second model situation, the cable was submitted to pure bending by means of two moments applied with same magnitude but opposite direction, generating a constant curvature radius. A four-point bending test was performed to verify the numerical model predictions. The geometry considered was for a 1×19 seale cable (two layers with nine rods each) lang lay (all rods twisted in the same direction). The lang lay configuration was adopted due to the better fatigue behaviour presented for this architecture [5]. However, the drawback is a higher torque relative to regular lay architecture, since all wires tend to rotate on the same way.

2 EVALUATING PULTRUDED RODS PROPERTIES

Individual rods that compose the cables were instrumented with strain gauges (SG) and submitted to tensile stress test (ASTM D3039 [6]) to evaluate the ultimate tensile strain and longitudinal Young's modulus, and to compression to find the ultimate compressive strain (ASTM D695 [7]). Fig. 2 presents the tensile stress test setup while Fig. 3 displays force vs. strain curve for the five samples tested.

Figure 2: Tensile stress test on the rod equipped with SG.

Figure 3: Force vs. strain curve for five pultruded rods under tensile stress test.

Table 1 shows the ultimate strain (ϵ), longitudinal Young's modulus (E_1) and their standard deviation, where E_1 was evaluated by computing the slope of the stress vs. strain curve between strain values in the range of 0.004-0.008, showing coefficient of determination superior to 0.999 for all samples.

	SG 1	SG 2	SG 3	SG 4	SG 5	AVERAGE
E_1 (GPa)	136	124	130	138	136	132 ± 6
ϵ	0.0178	0.0180	0.0182	0.0170	0.0170	0.0176 ± 0.0006

Table 1: Longitudinal Young's modulus and ultimate strain measured from one single rod.

Compression tests were also performed on the rods, and the ultimate strain could be computed by the measured longitudinal Young's modulus and ultimate stress, resulting in a value of 0.004515.

3 EXPERIMENTAL TESTS ON THE 1×19 CABLE

3.1 Tensile stress test

Commercial 1×19 CFCC with epoxy resin were tested under tensile stress on the LAMEF (Physical Metallurgy Laboratory). This cable architecture cross-section is showed in Fig. 4. The samples had approximately 502.50 mm length and a pitch of 98.33 mm.

Figure 4: Cross-section of the tested cable drawn in CAD platform SolidWorks 2014®

Four samples were instrumented each one with two strain-gauges, positioned close to the specimen midspan, on the external layer, where both strain and force data were acquired during the tests using a 10 Hz sampling frequency. Despite of the maximum strain location occur at the core rod, it was decided to attach the strain gages on the external rods to avoid damaging the cable when assembling/disassembling it, also preventing the SG to be squashed by external rods if attached at the core rod. Fig. 5 shows the cable tensile test setup before and after the cable breakage.

Figure 5: a) Cable installation. b) Cable after rupture.

3.2 Four-point Bending test

The tests to investigate CFCC bending behaviour were performed at LAPOL (Laboratory of Polymers) according to ASTM D6272 [8], which specifies a span/diameter ratio of 16, and a loading speed of 5 mm/min for the tests, considering a support span of 200 mm and a 100 mm load span. All three samples were instrumented with two strain-gauges each, positioned at the top and bottom external rods close to the middle of the cable. The vertical displacement was measured at the two points where the loads were applied and in the middle of the cable (region of maximum displacement). Fig. 6 shows the bending test performed with same cable geometries from the tensile stress test. CFCCs were bent until an 11 mm displacement on the point of loading application was reached.

Figure 6: Four-point bending device before (a) and after (b) flexure extension (11 mm).

4 NUMERICAL MODEL

Based on the measured longitudinal Young's modulus, it was possible to use the new invariant-based method proposed by Tsai and Mello [9], who introduced the master-ply concept, which presents same normalized lamina stiffness properties, verified by computing results of 10 different carbon/epoxy lamina. The invariant-based theory provides good results for thermosetting resins reinforced with high volume fractions of carbon fibres. The values evaluated with Tsai-Mello method are shown in Table 2.

E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	E_3 (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)
132	7.47	7.47	0.330	0.330	0.500	5.13	5.13	1.57

Table 2: Engineering constraints used at numerical model.

where:

E_2 and E_3 are the cable Young's modulus transversal to the fibre orientation;

G_{12} and G_{23} are the cable in-plane shear modulus, and G_{13} is the cable out-plane shear modulus;

ν_{12} and ν_{13} are the cable in-plane major Poisson's ratios, and ν_{23} is the cable out-plane major Poisson's ratio.

These material properties were inserted in the finite element software Abaqus®, where a local coordinate system was defined to allow the engineering constraints to change its orientation as the external rods twist around the cable core rod. Fig. 7 illustrates the global (X , Y and Z) and local (1, 2 and 3) coordinate systems adopted for the simulations. Since an average ultimate strain of $17800 \mu\epsilon$ was experimentally found for the CFRP by testing rods individually, the numerical model experienced a loading until this strain could be reached in the core, who suffers high strains than the external layer rods. The strain data on the external layer were used for experimental comparison.

Figure 7: Global and local coordinate system, adopted to account for the orthotropic properties of CFRP.

In the tensile stress model, a force was applied at one of the cable edges, where all rotations and X and Y displacements were constrained. On the opposite edge all rotations and displacements were constrained (built-in edge).

In the bending case, two moments with same magnitude and opposite directions were applied at the cable ends, simulating only the loading span segment, where the bending moment is constant. One of the edges is free to translate in the Z direction, while the other is constrained. Only rotation along X -axis is allowed.

A single-layered 1×7 cable, with a more traditional geometry where all rods have the same diameter of 4.1 mm, was also implemented in Abaqus® for the same situations of the 1×19 seale cable. The same cross sectional area was adopted for both (92 mm^2) as comparison basis (same cable eight). However, their moment of inertia differs from 766 mm^4 (1×7) to 808 mm^4 (1×19).

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since the strains in directions 2 and 3 are relatively small as compared to the strain in direction 1, the maximum strain criterion was adopted for the tensile stress tests. Fig. 8 plots results numerically and experimentally obtained, where it can be seen that the experimentally measured average ultimate load of 160.4 kN differs 4.24% from the 153.9 kN numerical ultimate load prediction, while the strain average measured at the external rod in the breaking point ($11,530 \mu\epsilon$) presents a 0.37% difference as compared to the predicted ultimate strain ($11,570 \mu\epsilon$). The analytical solution proposed by Costello [10], which neglects friction between rods and considers the material as isotropic was also included for comparison ($E = E_1$, $G = G_{12}$ and $\nu = \nu_{12}$ for simplification). Its behaviour is linear, and the load at rupture according to him is 16% above the experimental values.

Figure 8: Tensile stress response of the 1×19 seale cable

The compressive strain observed in experimental and numerical models during the rods accommodation only appears on the external rods, arising from the flexure contact stress when rods first touch each other.

Concerning the bending behaviour, after an average strain of 0.16% (1,600 $\mu\epsilon$), a non-linear behaviour can be observed due to buckling of upper rods, as reported in Fig. 9. Since the numerical model considered only linear elastic constraints, these effects could not be numerically reproduced. Comparing the numerical (16.5 kNmm) and experimental (19.1 kNmm) bending moment at the time non-linearity starts, they differ from 15.4%, and the curvature radius at this point was found from the FE model as being 318.2 mm. This difference between the two models occurs due to interaction between rods. The rods were modelled in order to not slip relative to an adjacent rod. In fact, the pre-tension imposed during the cable manufacturing process resulted in a very high friction between rods, but the main difference lies on the fact that united rods have a very large moment of inertia when compared to a geometry where they are all split, like in the numerical model.

Figure 10: Bending behaviour of 1×19 seale cable

Relative to the 1×7 cable, Figs. 11 and 12 show comparisons on the performance of these cables with respect to the already studied 1×19 seale cables for tensile and bending behaviour, respectively.

Figure 11: Tensile stress behaviour comparison between two different CFCC geometries.

Figure 12: Bending behaviour comparison between two different CFCC geometries.

Both of them were submitted to tensile strength until the ultimate strain of 1.76% (17,600 με) was achieved, and the 1×19 seale cable showed a slightly higher failure load. In the second case, they were bent until non-linearity starts (0.16% or 1,600 με), and due to its 1.6% higher moment of inertia relative to the 1×7 cable, the 1×19 again presented a better performance. While the seale cable could support a 318.6 mm radius of curvature, the 1×7 starts permanent strains at 536.4 mm.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The performance of a 1×19 cable under tensile stress was evaluated analytically, experimentally and numerically. However, due to simplifications of the analytical solution considered, it was not able

to predict the tensile behaviour as accurately as the numerical solution did (4.24% error). As reported by Ghoreishi *et al.* [11], who analysed many different analytical solutions including the one proposed by Costello [10], analytical predictions lose accuracy for low helix angles, which is the case for the studied CFCC. The numerous rods in contact also contributed with such variance, since analytical model neglects friction.

Relative to the bending behaviour, numerical models could predict experimental results only for small strains due to the premature non-linear behaviour presented by the cable. The minimum value of 318.6 mm was considered for the curvature radius in order to avoid non-linearity when bending the CFCC over a sheave or spool.

In comparison with the traditional 1×7 cable construction, 1×19 showed superiority in both cases for an equal cross-section area. This difference occurs due to a stress concentration at the core for the tensile stress case and due to a lower moment of inertia in the bending case.

It is possible to infer that CFCC are able to substitute steel cables for mooring offshore structures like TLPs. They proved to be stiff enough to prevent large displacements on the platform deck, support heavy loadings, and be able to suffer low strains when bent over small radius of curvature relative to steel cables, since the applied pitch was relatively low.

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